

A REVIEW ON HETEROCYCLIC RINGS PRESENT IN DRUGS USED IN CANCER TREATMENT

Rasajna Guttala^{*1}, Udaya Kumari Tula², Kamidi Sunitha³, Dr. E. Usha Rani⁴, Dr. Jami Durga Ganesh⁵

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Koringa College of Pharmacy, Korangi, Andhra Pradesh, India.

²Research Scientist, Dsk Biopharma inc-112 Nova Dr Morrisvill North Carolina, Usa.

³Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Koringa College of Pharmacy, Kornagi, Andhra Pradesh, India.

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Pydah College of Pharmacy, Patavala, Andhra Pradesh, India.

⁵Director Operations, Sitra Pharmaceuticals, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

***Corresponding Author: Prof. Rasajna Guttala**

Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Koringa College of Pharmacy, Korangi, Andhra Pradesh, India. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17746502>

How to cite this Article: Rasajna Guttala*, Udaya Kumari Tula, Kamidi Sunitha, Dr. E. Usha Rani, Dr. Jami Durga Ganesh. (2025). A REVIEW ON HETEROCYCLIC RINGS PRESENT IN DRUGS USED IN CANCER TREATMENT. European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 12(12), 88–105.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 31/10/2025

Article Revised on 21/11/2025

Article Published on 01/12/2025

ABSTRACT

Cancer which is an uncontrollable cell division that can occur in any part of the body, As our Human body is made up of no of billions of cells, depending upon place of origin there are several types of cancer, The drugs used in treatment of cancer has contain Heterocycles in them where the heteroatoms Sulphur, Oxygen and Nitrogen present in the structure are responsible for different modes of action like Tyrosine kinase Inhibitor, Protein Kinase Inhibitor, Epidermal Growth Factor receptor inhibitor, FLT3 Inhibitor, Alkylating agent, Topoisomerase-I inhibitor, Microtubule formation inhibitor and increase in pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic properties of the lead molecule like lipohilicity, Hydrogen bonding In this review we summarize current drugs used in cancer treatment, along with their mechanism of action and chemical structures.

KEYWORDS: Cancer, Heterocyclic ring, Pharmacokinetic, Pharmacodynamic, Mechanism of action.

INTRODUCTION

Heterocyclic compounds are inevitable part of many naturally occurring compounds which have therapeutic efficacy like alkaloids, carbohydrates, proteins hemoglobin, vitamins, In Humans they have significant contribution in many biological functions, one of them is formation of DNA and RNA where these heterocyclic rings are present as Nitrogen bases and contribute in cell division. So these nitrogen bases serve as molecular targets in treatment of Cancer.^[1] The aim of our present review is to consolidate different types of heterocyclic motifs used in the treatment of cancer.

Cancer can be lucidly defined as Uncontrollable cell division of cells which leads to abnormal cell growth. Its incidence has been increased in recent times According to Indian Council of Medical Research – National

Institute of Cancer Prevention and Research in India, estimated number of people living with Cancer is around 2.5 million with new cancer patients registered over 7 lakh annually and cancer related deaths account up to 5,56,400 annually.^[2]

The treatments of cancer involve clinical trials, chemotherapy, hormone therapy, personalized and targeted therapies, surgery, maintenance therapy, bone marrow/stem cell transplantation, immunotherapy and vaccination, radiation therapy and integrative medication.^[3] In cancer therapy and medications, heterocycle moieties play an important role in drug design due to their biological activity and versatility. Especially oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur-containing heterocyclic scaffolds were found in these types of anticancer drugs.^{[4][5]}

Anti-cancer drugs with Oxygen heterocycles

The oxygen containing heterocycles are important due to their natural abundance in various forms one such important derivative is Taxol which is an Anticancer

drug, other include Benzofuran, Coumarin, chromane Xanthene and all these belong to fused heterocycles where the heterocyclic ring fused with other ring systems.

Fig. 1: Heterocycles with oxygen as Hetero atom.

Some of the other oxygen containing ring systems used in cancer treatment are three membered e.g, cryptophycins, Triptolide.

Cryptophycins are a class of dioxadiazacyclohexadecenetrone cytotoxins with a potent ability to induce tubulin depolymerization. The cryptophycins were first isolated from the cultures of the *Nostoc* cyanobacteria in the early 1990s.^[6]

Cryptophycin-1 R = H
Cryptophycin-52 R = CH₃

Fig. 2: Cryptophycins.

Triptolide is an important diterpene active compound in *T. wilfordii*. Since 1972, when Kupchan et al. first isolated triptolide and found its significant anti-leukaemic effects.^[7]

Fig. 3: Triptolide.

Four membered Oxygen containing heterocyclic ring known as Oxetane is found in anti cancer drugs like Paclitaxel, Docetaxel, cabazitaxel, crenolanib.

Paclitaxel, initially named taxol, is a naturally occurring diterpenoid compound extracted from the Pacific yew tree, *Taxus brevifolia*.^[8]

Fig. 4: Paclitaxel.

Docetaxel is a complex diterpenoid molecule and a semisynthetic analogue of Paclitaxel.^[9]

Fig. 5: Docetaxel.

Cabazitaxel is a taxoid synthesized from 10-decacylbaccatin-iii, a compound found in *Taxus buccata*. It is a second generation semisynthetic microtubule inhibitor.^[10]

Fig. 6: Cabazitaxel.

Fig. 8: Octalactin.

Eight membered oxygen containing heterocyclic ring system known as oxocane is found in drugs like Laurencin, Octalactin B. Laurencin is cyclic bromoether isolated from *Laurencia* species (*Laurencia glandulifera*) of Rhodomelaceae family in 1965 by Irie et al.^[11]

Fig. 7: Laurencin.

Octalactin B belongs to class of β -lactones isolated from marine derived actinomycetes (streptomycetes) along with Octalactin A.^{[12],[13]}

Anti-Cancer drugs with Nitrogen Heterocycles

Most of the biologically active compounds in their chemical structure contains pentacyclic or hexacyclic ring structures with atleast one or two nitrogen atoms as hetero atoms^[14] like Adennine, Guanine, Cytosine, Thymine, Uracil, Nicotine, Tryptamine, thiamine, Riboflavin, Pyridoxal^[17] According to US FDA more than 50% of drugs have Nitrogen containing heterocycles in their structures.^{[15],[16]}

Current research for anti cancer drugs mainly focusses on development of the Pyrimidines, Quinoline, Carbazole, Pyridine, Imidazole, Benzimidazole, Triazole, beta lactams, Indole, Pyrazole, quinazoline, Quinoxaline, isatins.

Fig. 9: Heterocycles with Nitrogen as hetero atom.

Aziridine is a three membered nitrogen containing heterocyclic ring and widely found in natural products mainly alkaloids with antimicrobial and anti-cancer properties like mitomycin.

Pyridine is a six membered nitrogen containing heterocyclic compound found in camptothecin an anti-

cancer agent, following drugs approved by FDA as anti-cancer agents with nitrogen in their structure.

Alectinib Hydrochloride (2015)^[19], Brigatinib (2017)^[20], Lorlatinib (2018)^[21], Entrectinib (2019)^[22] are Anaplastic lymphoma kinase inhibitors primarily used in treatment of non-small cell lung cancer.

Fig. 10: Alectinib.

Fig. 11: Brigatinib.

Fig. 12: Lorlatinib.

Fig. 13: Entrectinib.

Midostaurin (2017)^[23,24], Gilteritinib fumarate (2018)^[25], Quizartinib (2018)^[26] are FMS like tyrosine kinase inhibitor used in various stages of acute myeloid leukemia.

Fig. 14: Midostaurin.

Fig. 15: Gilteritinib.

Fig. 16: Quizartinib.

Fig 25: Fruquintinib.

Fig 26: Anlotinib.

Acalabrutinib (2017)^[38], Zanubrutinib (2021)^[39] and Nilotinib (2007)^[104] are Tyrosine kinase inhibitors used in treatment of lung, breast and colon cancer.

Fig 27: Acalabrutinib.

Fig 28: Zanubrutinib.

Fig 29: Nilotinib.

Fedratinib (2019)^[40] is Janus kinase 2 (JAK2) inhibitor which is used in treatment of myeloproliferative neoplasm a rare type of Blood cancer.

Fig 30: Fedratinib.

Copanlisib (2014)^[41,42], Duvelisib (2018)^[45], Alpelisib (2019)^[89], and Idelalisib (2014)^[71,72] are Phosphatidylinositol 3-hydroxy kinase inhibitors used in

treatment of breast cancer, colorectal cancer, and hematologic malignancies like chronic lymphocytic leukemia and non-Hodgkin lymphoma.

Fig 31: Copanlisib.

Fig 32: Duvelisib.

Fig 33: Alpelisib.

Fig 34: Idelalisib.

Mocetinostat (2014)^[43,44] is Hydroxamic acid-based Histone deacetylase Inhibitor used in treatment of follicular lymphoma, Hodgkins lymphoma.

Fig. 35: Mocetinostat.

Oxaliplatin (2004)^[46,47] inhibits transcription of DNA used in treatment of colon and colorectal cancer.

Fig. 36: Oxaliplatin.

Irinotecan (2000)^[48,49] and Topotecan (1996)^[70] are Topoisomerase I inhibitors used in treatment of ovarian

cancer, small cell lung cancer, cervical cancer and cancer of colon and rectum.

Fig. 37: Irinotecan.

Fig. 38: Topotecan.

Cytarabine (1999)^[50,51], Gemcitabine (1996)^[52,53] are Pyrimidine nucleoside antimetabolite which are used in treatment of leukemia, pancreatic cancer; non-small-cell

lung cancer; breast, bladder, and ovarian cancers; and small-cell lung cancer.

Fig 39: Cytarabine

Fig 40: Gemcitabine

Trabectedin (2015)^[54,55], Bendamustine (2008)^[63] are alkylating agents, used in treatment of sickle cell anemia,

prostate cancer, blood cancer (acute lymphocytic leukemia), soft tissue sarcoma and Hodgkin's disease.

Fig 41: Trabectedin

Fig 42: Bendamustine

Kahalalide F (2004)^[56,57] is a lysosomal membrane disruptor, which is used in treatment of Prostate cancer,

breast cancer, colon cancer and under trials for other cancer types.

Fig. 43: Kahalide F.

Salinosporamide A (2004)^[58] an Inhibitor of the 20S proteasomes, used in treatment of Breast Cancer.

Fig. 44: Salinosporamide A.

Osimertinib (2015)^[59], Erlotinib (2004)^[95] and Gefitinib (2003)^[64] are Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor and

tyrosine kinase inhibitor and are used to treat Breast, Colon and Lung cancer.

Fig. 45: Osimertinib

Fig. 46: Erlotinib

Fig. 47: Gefitinib.

Soblidotin (2011)^[60] inhibits microtubule polymerisation used in treatment of sarcoma and lung cancer

Fig. 48: Soblidotin.

Selinexor (42) (2019)^[61,62] tumor suppressing protein activator, and used in treatment of multiple myeloma

Fig 49: Selinexor.

Abemaciclib (2017)^[65,66], Ribociclib (2018)^[67], Palbociclib (2016)^[78,79] are CDK 4 and CDK 6 inhibitor, currently used in treatment of metastatic breast cancer.

Fig. 50: Abemaciclib.

Fig. 51: Ribociclib.

Fig. 52: Palbociclib.

Mitomycin C (1974)^[68] double stranded DNA alkylating agent,

Fig. 53: Mitomycin C.

Porfimer (2002)^[69] Photodynamic therapy agent High-affinity immunoglobulin gamma Fc receptor I antagonist,

Fig. 54: Porfimer.

Acalabrutinib (2017)^[73] and Cabozantinib (2016)^[74,75] are tyrosine kinase inhibitor, used in treatment of leukemia

Fig. 55: Acalabrutinib.

Fig. 56: cabozantinib.

Lenvatinib (2018)^[76,77], Afatinib (2016)^[83,84], Gilteritinib (2018)^[87,88] are tyrosine kinase inhibitor and Trametinib (2013)^[80,81,82] are protein kinase inhibitor are used in

treatment of Acute myeloid leukemia and Non-small cell lung cancer.

Fig 57: Lenvatinib

Fig 58: Afatinib

Fig 59: Gilteritinib

Fig 60: Trametinib

Dabrafenib (2013)^[85,86] BRAF protein kinase inhibitor, used in treatment of metastatic melanoma.

Fig. 61: Dabrafenib.

Binimetinib (2018)^[90,91] and Crizotinib (2022)^[92,93] Small-molecule kinase inhibitor melanoma and non-small lung cancer treatment respectively.

Fig 62: Binimetinib

Fig 63: Crizotinib

Dactinomycin (2009)^[94] is a transcription inhibitor used in treatment of testicular cancer, Wilms' tumor, gestational trophoblastic neoplasia and Ewing's sarcoma.

Fig. 64: Dactinomycin.

Ibrutinib (2022)^[96,97] is a Bruton Tyrosine kinase inhibitor is used in B-cell lymphoma.

Fig. 65: Ibrutinib.

Lapatinib (2007)^[98] HER 2 and E.G.F.R antagonist used in treatment of metastatic breast cancer.

Fig. 66: Lapatinib.

Larotrectinib (2018)^[99,100] T.R.K. (Tropomyosin Receptor Kinase) inhibitor,

Fig. 67: Larotrectinib.

Mercaptopurine (2014)^[101] Hypoxanthine-guanine phospho ribosyl transferase, Amido phospho ribosyl transferase, Inosine-5'-monophosphate dehydrogenase Inhibitor used mainly in acute lymphoblastic leukemia.

Fig. 68: Mercaptopurine.

Methotrexate (1999)^[102,103] is a Thymidylate synthase and Dihydrofolate reductase Inhibitors used in treatment of leukemia, breast, skin, lung, head and neck cancers.

Fig. 69: Methotrexate.

Nilutamide (2016)^[105] is an Androgen receptor antagonist, used in treatment of Prostate cancer.

Fig. 70: Nilutamide.

Olaparib (2014)^[106,107] Poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP) inhibitor used in treatment of breast and ovarian cancer.

Fig. 71: Olaparib.

Anti-Cancer drugs with Sulphur Heterocycles

Sulphur containing Heterocycles are widely known for their anticancer properties as they can neutralise the drug resistance usually observed in chemotherapy with other drugs, Recent research shows that Sulforaphane found in cruciferous vegetables have significant anti-cancer property.^[108,109]

- agents: an overview. *Anti-Cancer Agents Med. Chem.*, 2020; 20(18): 2150-2168.
6. Amit Kumar, Jason White, R. James Christie, Nazzareno Dimasi, Changshou Gao, Chapter Twelve - Antibody-Drug Conjugates, Robert A. Goodnow, *Annual Reports in Medicinal Chemistry*, Academic Press, 2017; 50: 441-480, ISSN 0065-7743, ISBN9780128130698, <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.armc.2017.08.002>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0065774317300052>)
 7. Gao J, Zhang Y, Liu X, Wu X, Huang L, Gao W. Triptolide: pharmacological spectrum, biosynthesis, chemical synthesis and derivatives. *Theranostics*, 2021; 11(15): 7199-7221. doi:10.7150/thno.57745. <https://www.thno.org/v11p7199.htm>
 8. Awosika AO, Farrar MC, Jacobs TF. Paclitaxel. [Updated 2023 Nov 18]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK536917/>
 9. Mohammad Imran, Sadaf Saleem, Aiswarya Chaudhuri, Javed Ali, Sanjula Baboota, Docetaxel: An update on its molecular mechanisms, therapeutic trajectory and nanotechnology in the treatment of breast, lung and prostate cancer, *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*, 2020; 60: 101959, ISSN 1773-2247, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2020.101959>.
 10. L. Harivardhan Reddy, Didier Bazile, Drug delivery design for intravenous route with integrated physicochemistry, pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics: Illustration with the case of taxane therapeutics, *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*, 2014; 71: 34-57, ISSN 0169-409X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2013.10.007>.
 11. Akio Murai, Biosynthesis of Cyclic Bromoethers from Red Algae, Sir Derek Barton, Koji Nakanishi, Otto Meth-Cohn, *Comprehensive Natural Products Chemistry*, Pergamon, 1999; 303-324, ISBN 9780080912837, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-091283-7.00011-4>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780080912837000114>)
 12. Wang, J., Shi, Y., & Jiang, D. β -Lactone Derivatives and Their Anticancer Activities: A Short Review. *Current topics in medicinal chemistry*, 2021; 21(18): 1645-1656. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1568026621666210402142150>
 13. Tapiolas, Dianne M. and Roman, Mark and Fenical, William and Stout, Thomas J. and Clardy, Jon, Octalactins A and B: cytotoxic eight-membered-ring lactones from a marine bacterium, *Streptomyces* sp, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 1991; 113(12): 4682-4683. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00012a048>
 14. M.K. Parai, G. Panda A convenient synthesis of chiral amino acid derived 3,4-dihydro-2H-benzo[b][1,4]thiazines and antibiotic levofloxacin. *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2009; 50(33): 4703-4705. 10.1016/j.tetlet.2009.05.104
 15. J. Zhang, W. Liu, Q. Xue. The effect of molecular structure of heterocyclic compounds containing N, O and S on their tribological performance. *Wear*, 1999; 231(1): 65-70. 10.1016/S0043-1648(99)00111-8
 16. Andleeb Amin, Tanzeela Qadir, Praveen Kumar Sharma, Ishtiaq Jeelani, Hitoshi Abe, A Review on The Medicinal And Industrial Applications of N-Containing Heterocycles, *The Open Medicinal Chemistry Journal*, Volume 16, 2022, ISSN 1874-1045, <https://doi.org/10.2174/18741045-v16e2209010>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1874104522000105>)
 17. A REVIEW ON MEDICINALLY IMPORTANT NITROGEN HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS A.V.G.S.PRASAD & FALGUN PATEL R&D department Nandesari Drugs & Pharmaceuticals Pvt Ltd, 167-168 GIDC Industrial Estate, Nandesari, Vadodara, Gujarat 391340 international journal of novel research and development, 2024; 9(6).
 18. Larkins, E.; Blumenthal, G.M.; Chen, H.; He, K.; Agarwal, R.; Gieser, G.; Stephens, O.; Zahalka, E.; Ringgold, K.; Helms, W. FDA Approval: Alectinib for the Treatment of Metastatic, ALK-Positive Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer Following Crizotinib/Alectinib for ALK-Positive Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer. *Clin. Cancer Res.*, 2016; 22: 5171-5176.
 19. Sun, N.; Ren, C.; Kong, Y.; Zhong, H.; Chen, J.; Li, Y.; Zhang, J.; Zhou, Y.; Qiu, X.; Lin, H. Development of a Brigatinib degrader (SIAIS117) as a potential treatment for ALK positive cancer resistance. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2020; 193: 112190.
 20. Collier, T.L.; Normandin, M.D.; Stephenson, N.A.; Livni, E.; Liang, S.H.; Wooten, D.W.; Esfahani, S.A.; Stabin, M.G.; Mahmood, U.; Chen, J. Synthesis and preliminary PET imaging of ¹¹C and ¹⁸F isotopologues of the ROS1/ALK inhibitor lorlatinib. *Nat. Commun.*, 2017; 8: 1-12.
 21. Sartore-Bianchi, A.; Pizzutilo, E.G.; Marrapese, G.; Tosi, F.; Cerea, G.; Siena, S. Entrectinib for the treatment of metastatic NSCLC: Safety and efficacy. *Expert Rev. Anticancer. Ther.*, 2020; 20: 333-341.
 22. Kasamon, Y.L.; Ko, C.W.; Subramaniam, S.; Ma, L.; Yang, Y.; Nie, L.; Shord, S.; Przepiorka, D.; Farrell, A.T.; McKee, A.E. FDA approval summary: Midostaurin for the treatment of advanced systemic mastocytosis. *Oncologist*, 2018; 23: 1511-1519.
 23. Liang, X.; Wu, P.; Yang, Q.; Xie, Y.; He, C.; Yin, L.; Yin, Z.; Yue, G.; Zou, Y.; Li, L. An update of new small-molecule anticancer drugs approved from 2015 to 2020. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2021; 220: 113473.
 24. Tzogani, K.; Røshol, H.; Olsen, H.H.; Aas, I.B.; Dalhus, M.L.; Håkonsen, G.D.; Nilssen, L.S.; Lindberg, V.; Økvist, M.; Bolstad, B. The European

- Medicines Agency review of Gilteritinib (Xospata) for the treatment of adult patients with relapsed or refractory acute myeloid leukemia with an FLT3 mutation. *Oncologist*, 2020; 25: e1070–e1076.
25. Gunawardane, R.N.; Nepomuceno, R.R.; Rooks, A.M.; Hunt, J.P.; Ricono, J.M.; Belli, B.; Armstrong, R.C. Transient exposure to quizartinib mediates sustained inhibition of FLT3 signaling while specifically inducing apoptosis in FLT3-activated leukemia cells. *Mol. Cancer Ther.*, 2013; 12: 438–447.
 26. Benner, B.; Good, L.; Quiroga, D.; Schultz, T.E.; Kassem, M.; Carson, W.E.; Cherian, M.A.; Sardesai, S.; Wesolowski, R. Pexidartinib, a novel small molecule CSF-1R inhibitor in use for tenosynovial giant cell tumor: A systematic review of pre-clinical and clinical development. *Drug Des. Dev. Ther.*, 2020; 14: 1693.
 27. Butterworth, S.; Cross, D.A.; Finlay, M.R.V.; Ward, R.A.; Waring, M.J. The structure-guided discovery of osimertinib: The first US FDA approved mutant selective inhibitor of EGFR T790M. *Medchemcomm*, 2017; 8: 820–822.
 28. Zhang, W.; Fan, Y.-F.; Cai, C.-Y.; Wang, J.-Q.; Teng, Q.-X.; Lei, Z.-N.; Zeng, L.; Gupta, P.; Chen, Z.-S. Olmutinib (BI1482694/HM61713), a novel epidermal growth factor receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitor, reverses ABCG2-mediated multidrug resistance in cancer cells. *Front. Pharmacol.*, 2018; 9: 1097.
 29. Singh, H.; Walker, A.J.; Amiri-Kordestani, L.; Cheng, J.; Tang, S.; Balcazar, P.; Barnett-Ringgold, K.; Palmby, T.R.; Cao, X.; Zheng, N. US Food and Drug Administration Approval: Neratinib for the Extended Adjuvant Treatment of Early-Stage HER2-Positive Breast Cancer FDA Approval Summary: Neratinib. *Clin. Cancer Res.*, 2018; 24: 3486–3491.
 30. Lavacchi, D.; Mazzoni, F.; Giaccone, G. Clinical evaluation of dacomitinib for the treatment of metastatic non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC): Current perspectives. *Drug Des. Dev. Ther.*, 2019; 13: 3187.
 31. Li, X.; Wang, B. Pharmaceutically Acceptable Salt of (e)-n-[4-[[3-chloro-4-(2-Pyridylmethoxy) phenyl] amino]-3-cyano-7-ethoxy-6-quinolyl]-3-[(2r)-1-methylpyrrolidin-2-yl] prop-2-enamide, Preparation Method Thereof, and Medical Use Thereof. US Patent Application No. 14/001,778: 2013.
 32. Zhou, C.; Xie, L.; Liu, W.; Zhang, L.; Zhou, S.; Wang, L.; Chen, J.; Li, H.; Zhao, Y.; Zhu, B. Absorption, metabolism, excretion, and safety of [¹⁴C] almonertinib in healthy Chinese subjects. *Ann. Transl. Med.*, 2021; 9: 867.
 33. Hao, Z.; Wang, P. Lenvatinib in management of solid tumors. *Oncologist*, 2020; 25: e302–e310.
 34. Sochacka-Ćwikła, A.; Mączyński, M.; Regiec, A. FDA-Approved Small Molecule Compounds as Drugs for Solid Cancers from Early 2011 to the End of 2021. *Molecules*, 2022; 27: 2259.
 35. Zhang, Y.; Zou, J.-Y.; Wang, Z.; Wang, Y. Fruquintinib: A novel antivasculature endothelial growth factor receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitor for the treatment of metastatic colorectal cancer. *Cancer Manag. Res.*, 2019; 11: 7787.
 36. Shen, G.; Zheng, F.; Ren, D.; Du, F.; Dong, Q.; Wang, Z.; Zhao, F.; Ahmad, R.; Zhao, J. Anlotinib: A novel multi-targeting tyrosine kinase inhibitor in clinical development. *J. Hematol. Oncol.*, 2018; 11: 1–11.
 37. Isaac, K.; Mato, A.R. Acalabrutinib and its therapeutic potential in the treatment of chronic lymphocytic leukemia: A short review on emerging data. *Cancer Manag. Res.*, 2020; 12: 2079.
 38. Guo, Y.; Liu, Y.; Hu, N.; Yu, D.; Zhou, C.; Shi, G.; Zhang, B.; Wei, M.; Liu, J.; Luo, L. Discovery of zanubrutinib (BGB-3111), a novel, potent, and selective covalent inhibitor of Bruton's tyrosine kinase. *J. Med. Chem.*, 2019; 62: 7923–7940.
 39. Palmer, J.; Mesa, R. The role of fedratinib for the treatment of patients with primary or secondary myelofibrosis. *Ther. Adv. Hematol.*, 2020; 11: 2040620720925201.
 40. Markham, A. Copanlisib: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2017; 77: 2057–2062.
 41. Dreyling, M.; Morschhauser, F.; Bouabdallah, K.; Bron, D.; Cunningham, D.; Assouline, S.; Verhoef, G.; Linton, K.; Thieblemont, C.; Vitolo, U. Phase II study of copanlisib, a PI3K inhibitor, in relapsed or refractory, indolent or aggressive lymphoma. *Ann. Oncol.*, 2017; 28: 2169–2178.
 42. Bumber, Y.; Younes, A.; Garcia-Manero, G. Mocetinostat (MGCD0103): A review of an isotype-specific histone deacetylase inhibitor. *Expert Opin. Investig. Drugs*, 2011; 20: 823–829.
 43. Karandish, F.; Haldar, M.K.; You, S.; Brooks, A.E.; Brooks, B.D.; Guo, B.; Choi, Y.; Mallik, S. Prostate-specific membrane antigen targeted polymersomes for delivering mocetinostat and docetaxel to prostate cancer cell spheroids. *ACS Omega*, 2016; 1: 952–962.
 44. Rodrigues, D.A.; Sagrillo, F.S.; Fraga, C.A. Duvelisib: A 2018 novel FDA-approved small molecule inhibiting phosphoinositide 3-kinases. *Pharmaceuticals*, 2019; 12: 69.
 45. Ibrahim, A.; Hirschfeld, S.; Cohen, M.H.; Griebel, D.J.; Williams, G.A.; Pazdur, R. FDA drug approval summaries: Oxaliplatin. *Oncologist*, 2004; 9: 8–12.
 46. Monneret, C. Platinum anticancer drugs. From serendipity to rational design. In *Annales Pharmaceutiques Francaises*; Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2011; 286–295.
 47. Dean, L. Irinotecan therapy and UGT1A1 genotype. In *Medical Genetics Summaries*; National Center for Biotechnology Information (US): Bethesda, MD, USA, 2012; updated 2018.
 48. Bailly, C. Irinotecan: 25 years of cancer treatment. *Pharmacol. Res.*, 2019; 148: 104398.
 49. El-Subbagh, H.I.; Al-Badr, A.A. Cytarabine. In *Profiles of Drug Substances, Excipients and*

- Related Methodology*; Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2009; 34: 37–113.
50. Baker, W.J.; Royer Jr, G.L.; Weiss, R.B. Cytarabine and neurologic toxicity. *Oncology*, 1991; 9: 679–693.
 51. Noble, S.; Goa, K.L. Gemcitabine. *Drugs*, 1997; 54: 447–472.
 52. Paroha, S.; Verma, J.; Dubey, R.D.; Dewangan, R.P.; Molugulu, N.; Bapat, R.A.; Sahoo, P.K.; Kesharwani, P. Recent advances and prospects in gemcitabine drug delivery systems. *Int. J. Pharm.*, 2021; 592: 120043.
 53. Ganjoo, K.N.; Patel, S.J. Trabectedin: An anticancer drug from the sea. *Expert Opin. Pharmacother*, 2009; 10: 2735–2743.
 54. Barone, A.; Chi, D.-C.; Theoret, M.R.; Chen, H.; He, K.; Kufirin, D.; Helms, W.S.; Subramaniam, S.; Zhao, H.; Patel, A. FDA Approval Summary: Trabectedin for Unresectable or Metastatic Liposarcoma or Leiomyosarcoma Following an Anthracycline-Containing Regimen. *Clin. Cancer Res.*, 2017; 23: 7448–7453.
 55. Brown, A.P.; Morrissey, R.L.; Faircloth, G.T.; Levine, B.S. Preclinical toxicity studies of kahalalide F, a new anticancer agent: Single and multiple dosing regimens in the rat. *Cancer Chemother. Pharmacol*, 2002; 50: 333–340.
 56. Nastrucci, C.; Cesario, A.; Russo, P. Anticancer drug discovery from the marine environment. *Recent Pat. Anti-Cancer Drug Discov.*, 2012; 7: 218–232.
 57. Fenical, W.; Jensen, P.R.; Palladino, M.A.; Lam, K.S.; Lloyd, G.K.; Potts, B.C. Discovery and development of the anticancer agent salinosporamide A (NPI-0052). *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2009; 17: 2175–2180.
 58. Greig, S.L. Osimertinib: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2016; 76: 263–273.
 59. Watanabe, J.; Minami, M.; Kobayashi, M. Antitumor activity of TZT-1027 (Soblidotin). *Anticancer Res.*, 2006; 26: 1973–1981.
 60. Syed, Y.Y. Selinexor: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2019; 79: 1485–1494.
 61. Podar, K.; Shah, J.; Chari, A.; Richardson, P.G.; Jagannath, S. Selinexor for the treatment of multiple myeloma. *Expert Opin. Pharmacother*, 2020; 21: 399–408.
 62. Leong, H.; Bonk, M.E. Therapeutics: Bendamustine (Treanda) for chronic lymphocytic leukemia: A brief overview. *Pharm. Ther.*, 2009; 34: 73.
 63. Cohen, M.H.; Williams, G.A.; Sridhara, R.; Chen, G.; Pazdur, R. FDA drug approval summary: Gefitinib (ZD1839)(Iressa[®]) tablets. *Oncologist*, 2003; 8: 303–306.
 64. Kim, E.S. Abemaciclib: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2017; 77: 2063–2070.
 65. Voli, L.A.; Mamyrbékova, J.A.; Bazureau, J.-P. Abemaciclib, a recent novel FDA-Approved small molecule inhibiting cyclin-dependant kinase 4/6 for the treatment of metastatic breast cancer: A mini-review. *Open J. Med. Chem.*, 2020; 10: 128–138.
 66. Shah, A.; Bloomquist, E.; Tang, S.; Fu, W.; Bi, Y.; Liu, Q.; Yu, J.; Zhao, P.; Palmby, T.R.; Goldberg, K.B. FDA Approval: Ribociclib for the Treatment of Postmenopausal Women with Hormone Receptor–Positive HER2–Negative Advanced or Metastatic Breast Cancer. *Clin. Cancer Res.*, 2018; 24: 2999–3004.
 67. Dimou, A.; Syrigos, K.N.; Saif, M.W. Is there a role for mitomycin C in metastatic colorectal cancer? Expert opinion on investigational drugs. *Expert Opin. Investig. Drugs*, 2010; 19: 723–735.
 68. Benayoun, L.; Schaffer, M.; Bril, R.; Gingis-Velitski, S.; Segal, E.; Nevelsky, A.; Satchi-Fainaro, R.; Shaked, Y. Porfimer-sodium (Photofrin-II) in combination with ionizing radiation inhibits tumor-initiating cell proliferation improves glioblastoma treatment efficacy. *Cancer Biol. Ther.*, 2013; 14: 64–74.
 69. Hörmann, V.; Kumi-Diaka, J.; Durity, M.; Rathinavelu, A. Anticancer activities of genistein-topotecan combination in prostate cancer, cells. *J. Cell. Mol. Med.*, 2012; 16: 2631–2636.
 70. Shah, A.; Mangaonkar, A. Idelalisib: A novel PI3K δ inhibitor for chronic lymphocytic leukemia. *Ann. Pharmacother*, 2015; 49: 1162–1170.
 71. Zirlik, K.; Veelken, H. Idelalisib. *Small Mol. Hematol*, 2018; 243–264.
 72. Markham, A.; Dhillon, S. Acalabrutinib: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2018; 78: 139–145.
 73. Singh, H.; Brave, M.; Beaver, J.A.; Cheng, J.; Tang, S.; Zahalka, E.; Palmby, T.R.; Venugopal, R.; Song, P.; Liu, Q. Food Drug Administration approval: Cabozantinib for the treatment of advanced renal cell carcinoma. *Ther. Adv. Urol.*, 2017; 23: 330–335.
 74. Duke, E.S.; Barone, A.K.; Chatterjee, S.; Mishra-Kalyani, P.S.; Shen, Y.L.; Isikwei, E.; Zhao, H.; Bi, Y.; Liu, J.; Rahman, N.A. FDA Approval Summary: Cabozantinib for Differentiated Thyroid Cancer. *Clin. Cancer Res.*, 2022; 28: 4173–4177.
 75. Arora, S.; Balasubramaniam, S.; Zhang, W.; Zhang, L.; Sridhara, R.; Spillman, D.; Mathai, J.P.; Scott, B.; Golding, S.J.; Coory, M. FDA Approval Summary: Pembrolizumab plus Lenvatinib for Endometrial Carcinoma a Collaborative International Review under Project Orbis. FDA Approval: Pembrolizumab plus, lenvatinib; Project Orbis. *Clin. Cancer Res.*, 2020; 26: 5062–5067.
 76. Nair, A.; Reece, K.; Donoghue, M.B.; Yuan, W.; Rodriguez, L.; Keegan, P.; Pazdur, R. FDA supplemental approval summary: Lenvatinib for the treatment of unresectable hepatocellular carcinoma. *Oncologist*, 2021; 26: e484–e491.
 77. Lu, J. Oncology: Palbociclib: A first-in-class CDK4/CDK6 inhibitor for the treatment of hormone-receptor positive advanced breast cancer. *J. Hematol. Oncol*, 2015; 8: 1–3.

78. Roskoski, R. Cyclin-dependent protein kinase inhibitors including palbociclib as anticancer drugs. *Pharmacol. Res.*, 2016; 107: 249–275.
79. Wright, C.J.; McCormack, P.L. Trametinib: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2013; 73: 1245–1254.
80. Zeiser, R.; Andrlová, H.; Meiss, F. Trametinib (GSK1120212). *Small Mol. Oncol*, 2018; 91–100.
81. Odogwu, L.; Mathieu, L.; Blumenthal, G.; Larkins, E.; Goldberg, K.B.; Griffin, N.; Bijwaard, K.; Lee, E.Y.; Philip, R.; Jiang, X. FDA approval summary: Dabrafenib and trametinib for the treatment of metastatic non-small cell lung cancers harboring BRAF V600E mutations. *Oncologist*, 2018; 23: 740–745.
82. Dunto, R.T.; Keating, G.M. Afatinib: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2013; 73: 1503–1515.
83. Helena, A.Y.; Pao, W. Targeted therapies: Afatinib—New therapy option for EGFR-mutant lung cancer. *Nat. Rev. Clin. Oncol*, 2013; 10: 551.
84. Ballantyne, A.D.; Garnock-Jones, K.P. Dabrafenib: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2013; 73: 1367–1376.
85. Menzies, A.M.; Long, G.V.; Murali, R. Dabrafenib and its potential for the treatment of metastatic melanoma. *Drug Des. Dev. Ther.*, 2012; 6: 391.
86. Dhillon, S. Gilteritinib: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2019; 79: 331–339.
87. Perl, A.E.; Martinelli, G.; Cortes, J.E.; Neubauer, A.; Berman, E.; Paolini, S.; Montesinos, P.; Baer, M.R.; Larson, R.A.; Ustun, C. Gilteritinib or chemotherapy for relapsed or refractory FLT3-mutated AML. *N. Engl. J. Med.*, 2019; 18: 1728–1740.
88. Markham, A. Alpelisib: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2019; 79: 1249–1253.
89. Shirley, M. Encorafenib and binimetinib: First global approvals. *Drugs*, 2018; 78: 1277–1284.
90. Tran, B.; Cohen, M.S. The discovery and development of binimetinib for the treatment of melanoma. *Expert Opin. Drug Discov*, 2020; 15: 745–754.
91. Kazandjian, D.; Blumenthal, G.M.; Chen, H.-Y.; He, K.; Patel, M.; Justice, R.; Keegan, P.; Pazdur, R. FDA approval summary: Crizotinib for the treatment of metastatic non-small cell lung cancer with anaplastic lymphoma kinase rearrangements. *Oncologist*, 2014; 19: e5–e11.
92. O'Bryant, C.L.; Wenger, S.D.; Kim, M.; Thompson, L.A. Crizotinib: A new treatment option for ALK-positive non-small cell lung cancer. *Ann. Pharmacother*, 2013; 47: 189–197.
93. Slayton, R.E.; Park, R.C.; Silverberg, S.G.; Shingleton, H.; Creasman, W.T.; Blessing, J.A. Vincristine, dactinomycin, and cyclophosphamide in the treatment of malignant germ cell tumors of the ovary. A Gynecologic Oncology Group Study (a final report). *Cancer*, 1985; 56: 243–248.
94. Cohen, M.H.; Johnson, J.R.; Chen, Y.-F.; Sridhara, R.; Pazdur, R. FDA drug approval summary: Erlotinib (Tarceva®) tablets. *Oncologist*, 2005; 10: 461–466.
95. Cameron, F.; Sanford, M. Ibrutinib: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2014; 74: 263–271.
96. De Claro, R.A.; McGinn, K.M.; Verdun, N.; Lee, S.-L.; Chiu, H.-J.; Saber, H.; Brower, M.E.; Chang, C.G.; Pfuma, E.; Habtemariam, B. FDA approval: Ibrutinib for patients with previously treated mantle cell lymphoma and previously treated chronic lymphocytic leukemia. *Clin. Cancer Res.*, 2015; 21: 3586–3590.
97. Ryan, Q.; Ibrahim, A.; Cohen, M.H.; Johnson, J.; Ko, C.-W.; Sridhara, R.; Justice, R.; Pazdur, R. FDA drug approval summary: Lapatinib in combination with capecitabine for previously treated metastatic breast cancer that overexpresses HER-2. *Oncologist*, 2008; 13: 1114–1119.
98. Scott, L. Larotrectinib: First global approval. *Drugs*, 2019; 79: 201–206.
99. Federman, N.; McDermott, R. Larotrectinib, a highly selective tropomyosin receptor kinase (TRK) inhibitor for the treatment of TRK fusion cancer. *Expert Rev. Clin. Pharmacol*, 2019; 12: 931–939.
100. Neerman, M.F.; Chen, H.-T.; Parrish, A.R.; Simanek, E.E. Reduction of drug toxicity using dendrimers based on melamine. *Mol. Pharm.*, 2004; 1: 390–393.
101. Weinstein, G.D. Drugs five years later: Methotrexate. *Ann. Intern. Med.*, 1977; 86: 199–204.
102. Moshikur, R.M.; Chowdhury, M.R.; Wakabayashi, R.; Tahara, Y.; Moniruzzaman, M.; Goto, M.J. Ionic liquids with methotrexate moieties as a potential anticancer prodrug: Synthesis, characterization and solubility evaluation. *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2019; 278: 226–233.
103. DeRemer, D.L.; Ustun, C.; Natarajan, K. Nilotinib: A second-generation tyrosine kinase inhibitor for the treatment of chronic myelogenous leukemia. *Clin. Ther.*, 2008; 30: 1956–1975.
104. Harris, M.G.; Coleman, S.G.; Faulds, D.; Crisp, P. Nilutamide: A review of its pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic properties, and therapeutic efficacy in prostate cancer. *Drugs Aging*, 1993; 3: 9–25.
105. Kim, G.; Ison, G.; McKee, A.E.; Zhang, H.; Tang, S.; Gwise, T.; Sridhara, R.; Lee, E.; Tzou, A.; Philip, R. FDA Approval Summary: Olaparib Monotherapy in Patients with Deleterious Germline BRCA-Mutated Advanced Ovarian Cancer Treated with Three or More Lines of Chemotherapy. *Clin. Cancer Res.*, 2015; 21: 4257–4261.
106. Caulfield, S.E.; Davis, C.C.; Byers, K.F. Olaparib: A novel therapy for metastatic breast cancer in patients with a BRCA1/2 mutation. *J. Adv. Pract. Oncol.*, 2019; 10: 167.
107. Asif Ali, Noohela Khan Muhammad, Nabeeha Kaleem, Waqas Ahmad, Salem Hussain Alharethi, Bandar Alharbi, Hassan H. Alhassan, et al., Anticancer properties of sulforaphane: Current

- insights at the molecular level *Front. Oncol.*, 2023; 13: 1168321.
108. Shuo Yuan, Bin Yu, Hong-Min Liu, New drug approvals for 2019: Synthesis and clinical applications, *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2020; 205: 112667, ISSN 0223-5234, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2020.112667>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0223523420306395>)
109. Zhen-Xi Niu, Ya-Tao Wang, Jin-Feng Sun, Peng Nie, Piet Herdewijn, Recent advance of clinically approved small-molecule drugs for the treatment of myeloid leukemia, *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2023; 261: 115827, ISSN 0223-5234, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2023.115827>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0223523423007948>)
110. Yulia L. Volodina, Alexander S. Tikhomirov, Lyubov G. Dezhenkova, Alla A. Ramonova, Anastasia V. Kononova, Daria V. Andreeva, Dmitry N. Kaluzhny, Dominique Schols, Mikhail M. Moisenovich, Andrey E. Shchekotikhin, Alexander A. Shtil, Thiophene-2-carboxamide derivatives of anthraquinone: A new potent antitumor chemotype, *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2021; 221: 113521, ISSN 0223-5234, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2021.113521>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0223523421003706>)
111. Villegas, C., González-Chavarría, I., Burgos, V., Iturra-Beiza, H., Ulrich, H., & Paz, C. Epothilones as Natural Compounds for Novel Anticancer Drugs Development. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 2023; 24(7): 6063. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24076063>
112. Er-Jun Hao, Yan Zhao, Min Yu, Xian-Jia Li, Ke-Xin Wang, Fu-Ying Su, Yu-Ru Liang, Yang Wang, Hai-Ming Guo, Discovery, Synthesis, and Activity Evaluation of Novel Five-Membered Sulfur-Containing Heterocyclic Nucleosides as Potential Anticancer Agents In Vitro and In Vivo, *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2024; 67(15): 12553-12570, ISSN 1520-4804, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.4c00443>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1520480424003028>)
113. Ke-Jia Wu, Xie Liu, Suk-Yu Wong, Yuyang Zhou, Dik-Lung Ma, Chung-Hang Leung Synthesis and evaluation of dibenzothiophene analogues as Pin1 inhibitors for cervical cancer therapy *ACS Omega*, 2019; 4(5): 9228-9234.